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COQ10B is an IBD susceptibility pathway-associated gene.

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We report here discovery of the coenzyme COQ10B as an IBD susceptibility-associated pathway gene. COQ10B was co-regulated with SOD2, a NOD2 transcriptional target. The COQ10B gene product was activated by the PAMP muramyl dipeptide and dysregulated in the myeloid lineage in humans with Crohn's Disease.

1 **Results**

2 We identified COQ10B through whole transcription technologies, studying transcriptional control by IBD
3 associated genes including XIAP, TRIM22, ATG16L1 and NOD2.

4 Figure 1: COQ10B expression was closely associated with expression of the inflammasome cytokine
5 IL-1B and superoxide dismutase 2, SOD2.

6 Figure 2: SOD2 stage-specific expression in the hematopoietic compartment.

7 Figure 3: SOD2 expression was induced during HSC differentiation to multiple lineages including
8 granulocytes, megakaryocytes, monocytes and the lymphocytes.

9 Figure 4: SOD2 expression is activated by MDP.

10 Figure 5: SOD2 expression still was relatively modestly expressed in the monocyte at steady state but
11 strongly activated by the gram negative bacterial pattern MDP.

12 Figure 6: SOD2 expression was compromised (reduced) in primary monocytes of humans with Crohn's
13 Disease whose cells contained mutations (IBD-associated SNPs) in NOD2.

14 Figure 7: Quantify reduction in SOD2 induction in CD patient blood cells following MDP sensing

15 Figure 8: Defective SOD gene expression in Black syndrome macrophages

16 Figure 9: Expression of SOD2 and SOD1 in normal monocytes, in CD patient monocytes at baseline, and
17 in response to MDP exposure.

18 Figure 10: SOD1/2 regulation by oxLDL in macrophage.

- 19 • Study of NOD2 L1007P regulation of coenzymes and SOD1/2 in a cellular reporter system.
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